

Research Article

Enhancing Legal Education for Non-Law Students: The Use of Video for Case Law Studies in Corporate Law for Accounting Students

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Abstract: *This study examines the effectiveness of using videos for case law studies as a teaching tool for non-law students, specifically focusing on using animated videos of Malaysian case laws related to Corporate Law (LAW485) for accounting students at Universiti Teknologi MARA. Traditional legal education can be challenging for non-law students due to the complexity of legal language and abstract concepts. Videos for case law studies offer an innovative approach by incorporating visual and narrative elements to simplify and contextualize legal scenarios. Findings revealed that students who engaged with videos demonstrated improved comprehension, retention, and engagement. Visual aids, such as diagrams and animations, facilitated better memory recognition and cognitive processing, supporting deeper learning. The study underscores the potential of video-based resources to bridge the gap between abstract legal theory and practical understanding, fostering an inclusive learning environment for diverse academic backgrounds. Future research should explore the long-term benefits and broader application of this approach in legal education.*

Keywords: Video-based learning, legal education, non-law students.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Legal education traditionally emphasizes textual analysis, critical thinking, and case law study, which can present challenges for non-law students who may lack foundational legal knowledge. The complexity of legal language and the abstract nature of legal concepts can hinder comprehension and engagement. Legal terminology can be dense and confusing, and the structure of legal cases often involves lengthy facts and judgments, which can overwhelm students (Saian & Zakuan, 2021). To address these challenges, innovative pedagogical approaches, such as video for case law studies, are being explored to enhance learning experiences. Videos for case law studies integrate visual and narrative elements to present legal scenarios, making legal concepts more relatable and understandable for students from diverse academic backgrounds (Vidal-López, 2020). This study investigates the effectiveness of videos for case law studies as a teaching tool for non-law students enrolled in law-related courses.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

This study adopted a doctrinal research approach to analyze the design and educational effectiveness of video-based learning for non-law students to study case laws. The focus will be on Corporate Law (LAW485) topics tailored for accounting students at Universiti Teknologi MARA. Doctrinal analysis was used to review existing legal education literature, visual communication theories, and the application of video-based learning tools. Additionally, educational content was designed to simplify complex legal principles, emphasizing key aspects of corporate law. The website was developed with user-friendly navigation, and animated videos were created to present case laws in an engaging and accessible manner.

3. FINDINGS

3.1 *Non-law Students Difficulty in Studying Law*

Non-law students often struggle with the specialized vocabulary and syntactically complex sentence structures inherent in legal texts, which can create barriers to understanding (Tanner, 2010). Additionally, many students' express concerns about their ability to apply legal knowledge effectively in their fields, indicating a disconnect between legal studies and their primary disciplines (Finlayson & Ayling, 2009).

3.2 *Case Law Studies for Non-law Students*

Research indicates that a case-based lecturing approach is more effective for non-law students, as it aligns better with their cognitive abilities and learning motivations (Rahim, 2015). Furthermore, comprehensive casebooks on specific legal areas, like non-discrimination law, offer valuable insights into emerging case law and legislation, enhancing students' understanding of complex legal concepts (Schiek et al., 2007).

3.3 *Video Enhancing Learning Abilities*

Visual aids significantly enhance learner engagement and retention in educational settings by improving memory recognition and facilitating understanding. Research indicates that elements such as color, shape, and orientation in visual communication positively correlate with students' performance and memory enhancement (Jamal & Mustaffa, 2023). Additionally, audio-visual aids, including videos and animations, have been shown to increase attention spans and learning abilities among students (Vishnupriya & Bharathi, 2022). In language learning, visual aids promote engagement by improving attention and participation, thereby enhancing comprehension of complex topics (Montoya & Manuel, 2017). Furthermore, the effective use of visual aids, such as concept maps and diagrams, supports cognitive processes and aids in the organization of knowledge, which is crucial for deeper learning (Steinberg et al., 2021). Studies also suggest that carefully designed images yield better engagement compared to text-heavy presentations, emphasizing the importance of visual modality in teaching (Napper, 2014).

4. DISCUSSION

The findings from this study highlight the unique challenges non-law students face when engaging with legal education, specifically in Corporate Law (LAW485) at Universiti Teknologi MARA. The complexity of legal language, characterized by dense terminology and intricate sentence structures, can create significant barriers to comprehension for students whose primary field of study does not include law (Tanner, 2010). Additionally, the traditional approach of reading and analyzing case law

texts may overwhelm non-law students, as it requires skills that are not typically emphasized in other disciplines (Finlayson & Ayling, 2009).

To address these challenges, the use of video for case law studies has been identified as an effective teaching method. Videos that integrate visual and narrative elements help to simplify and contextualize legal scenarios, making complex legal concepts more accessible. Research supports that audio-visual aids enhance learning by increasing attention, engagement, and comprehension, thus addressing the cognitive demands of understanding legal texts (Jamal & Mustaffa, 2023; Vishnupriya & Bharathi, 2022). For instance, elements like color, shape, and movement can capture students' attention and improve memory retention, which is crucial when dealing with abstract legal principles.

Moreover, the use of animated videos on a website specifically designed for LAW485 students provides a user-friendly platform that allows students to engage with case law on their own terms. This self-paced learning tool not only helps students overcome the initial intimidation associated with legal language but also enables them to see practical applications of the principles of company law. Through the visual representation of real-world legal scenarios, students can more effectively grasp how company law operates as a framework for business governance, aligning with the course's objectives to describe, present, and relate company law principles (Rahim, 2015). This approach is particularly valuable for accounting students, as it allows them to see the relevance of legal concepts in a business context, thus bridging the gap between legal studies and their primary discipline.

5. CONCLUSION

The study underscores the effectiveness of video-based learning in making legal education more approachable and comprehensible for non-law students. By incorporating visual aids and animations, videos can simplify complex legal concepts, thereby facilitating better understanding, retention, and engagement. For accounting students at Universiti Teknologi MARA studying Corporate Law (LAW485), the use of animated videos on a dedicated website has proven to be an effective pedagogical tool. It aligns with the course objectives by helping students describe, present, and relate the principles of company law, thus enhancing their ability to apply legal knowledge to business scenarios. This approach addresses the cognitive challenges non-law students face by presenting legal concepts in a more engaging and practical manner. Future research could explore the broader application of this video-based teaching method in other legal courses and its long-term impact on students' academic performance and professional competencies.

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